

Community-Based Destination Sustainable Development: Case of Cicada Walking Street, Hua Hin, Thailand

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Abstract—This paper aims to study the role and activities of the participants and the impact of activities created in the local area in order to sustainably develop the local areas. This study applied both qualitative and quantitative approaches presented in descriptive style; the data was collected via survey, observation and in-depth interviews with samples. The results illustrated five sorts of roles of participants of the Cicada Walking-street and four types of creative activities; recreation based, art based, cultural based, and live events. Integration of local characteristics, arts and cultures were presented creatively and interestingly. Participants are various. The roles of the participants found in the Cicada Market are group of the property and area management, entrepreneurs, leisure (entertaining persons), local people, and tourists. The good impacts on local communities are those in terms of economy, environmental friendly and local arts and cultures promoting. On the other hand, the traffic congestion, waste and the increasing of energy consumption are negative impacts from area development.

Keywords—Creative Tourism Activity, Destination Development, Sustainable Development, Walking Street.

I. INTRODUCTION

THAILAND have been recognized as a popular destination by the international tourists worldwide. Tourist arrivals in 2006 accounted for 13.82 million. In 2007, the tourism sector showed mixed results, as political and security uncertainties in the wake of the September 2006 coupled to fewer East Asian arrivals. But double-digit growth from European, Middle Eastern and South Asian visitors could help the sector reach official targets of 14.8 million visitors and revenues of 547 billion baht for the full year. Visitor arrivals in the first nine months of the year at Suvarnabhumi Airport rose by 4% to 7.47 million [12].

In Thailand, tourism is a major economic factor which contributed an estimated 6.7% to GDP of the country in 2007. [1] Tourism development has recently grown into a significant economic force. Combined with local and regional development policies, it has increased the pace of minority group integration into national and world economies. Many beautiful destinations in Thailand have been exotic destinations since the 1970s. On June 1, 2013, Time magazine reported that Bangkok, the capital city of Thailand was identified as the most visited city in the world according to the third annual Global Destination Cities Index released by

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MasterCard. [2] As same as, Suvarnabhumi Airport was claimed as the most frequently geographically referred place on the famous social network called 'Instagram' in 2013. [3] The promotion of tourism has been identified as a key strategy that can lead to economic progress, community development and poverty relief in the developing world. The Tourism Authority of Thailand (TAT) uses the slogan "Amazing Thailand" to promote Thailand internationally. Many extensive tourisms, such as health and wellness tourism, golf tourism, cultural tourism, eco-tourism, and adventure tourism, have been developed and promoted. In the last few years, an inbound international tourist numbers has decrease as effects of political situations and some natural disasters.

Cicada Market and Cicada Walking-Street or sometimes called as Chakachan Market (Chakachan means cicada in Thai language) is located at Hua Hin, Prachaup Khiri Khan Province, Thailand. The name of 'Cicada' was named after a cicada, a long- life cycle insect. The ideal name of 'Cicada' was brought to represent the fully interesting nightlife activities in this place where it was operated to combines variety of activities, arts (from an underground arts to an international arts), fascinating events and peaceful green atmosphere through day and night. In addition, Cicada Market was created with the aim of being a connection centre for all artists, creators, designers, tourists, students and community through integrating culture and arts with lifestyles.

Cicada market usually generally referred as the Cicada walking-street stages their position as a Community (C) of Identity (I) Culture (C) Arts (A) and Dynamic (D) Activities (A).

As an art market with the atmosphere that filled with characteristic of Hua Hin, Cicada Market is a source of contemporary art in various fields, including the invention of handmade decorative items, fashion clothes, collective secondhand items and SME products with innovative ideas to be displayed and sold in open-style mat and shop. It is the place that offers opportunities for all people to participate or to demonstrate their creativities through a various types of creative activities, workshops, exhibitions, performances, dance, music and fine arts for examples. The market is open on Friday to Sunday from 16:00 to 22:00. The location is showered in light with sparkling decorations and surrounded by beautiful garden with many trees. The entire location features the abundance of shopping outlets and eateries, as well as a venue for live performances and art exhibitions.

Cicada Market is divided into four venues: Art A La Mode, Cicada Art Factory, Amphitheatre and Cicada Cuisine. [9]

Sasi Ampai Leisure Business (2013) [9], the property developing company, gives the details of Cicada walking street by explaining the place divided into four venues. First section called as Art A La Mode is where art and craft vendors alongside the paths on the site sell items of clothing, handmade bags, fashion accessories, souvenirs, crafts, used items and cards. Most of the vendors here are young people from art colleges, local vendors, or vendors from Bangkok and nearby. Second, at the centre, there are the two white buildings with raised floors serve as a venue for art exhibitions, called as "Cicada Art Factory". Exhibitions feature young artists with original style of their works, as well as those from further afield. The artists are rotated regularly to show the public the wealth of variety in terms of the artistic content, including illustrations, portraits, paintings, photos and sculptures. The concept of Art factory is to promote the young artists and to help them generate revenue with their original works. An amphitheatre-style venue provides a form of entertainment designed to educate as well as to amuse visitors. Visitors can enjoy edutainment activities performed by bands, dance troupes, or theatre groups. Definitely, these performances are rotated regularly to grab the attention of visitors. Also, this venue is to promote the work of talented artists in the performing arts field. Food zone called Cicada Cuisine where visitors can choose from a wide variety of local and international delights, such as grilled seafood, grilled pork satay, Pad Thai, Fried Mussels Thai Style, Chinese noodle, Korean B.B.Q, various forms of rice-based dishes, American and Italian pasta dishes, and variety of desserts. Also, many choices of drinks are served.

Cicada Market is still open to vendors of handicrafts and idea works, while the market is also open to proposals from artists, musicians, or other performers looking for a venue to perform their shows. No admission charge to Cicada Market, performances or exhibitions taking place are free of charge. [9].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Community Based Tourism

Community-based tourism development is receiving increased attention from a variety of sectors: For those in government and non-governmental organisations who have long been working with communities on wildlife and natural resource management, tourism enterprises are seen as one form of sustainable utilisation with potential to bring economic, as well as social, benefits to communities. For those in government and the private sector working to develop the Namibian tourism product, development in communal areas and involvement of local people is one essential (though until now relatively unexplored) element [4].

B. Sustainable Development

Sustainable tourism has become an increasingly popular field of research since the late 1980s. However, the sustainable

tourism debate is patchy, disjointed and often flawed with false assumptions and arguments [11].

Sustainable development, although a widely used phrase and idea, has many different meanings and therefore provokes many different responses. In broad terms, the concept of sustainable development is an attempt to combine growing concerns about a range of environmental issues with socio-economic issues. Hopwood, Mellor, and O'Brien (2005) [5] impressively define term of sustainable development as a specific ideal of concentrating on sustainable livelihoods and well-being rather than well-having and long term environmental sustainability, which requires a strong basis in principles that link the social and environmental to human equity.

The widespread rise of interest in, and support for, the concept of sustainable development is potentially an important shift in understanding relationships of humanity with nature and between people.

Hopwood, Bill, Mellor, Mary and O'Brien, Geoff (2005) [5] explained the concept of sustainable development as the result of the growing awareness of the global links between mounting environmental problems, socio-economic issues to do with poverty and inequality and concerns about a healthy future for humanity. It strongly links environmental and socio-economic issues.

The first important use of the term was in 1980 in the World Conservation Strategy [6]. This process of bringing together environmental and socio-economic questions was most famously expressed in the Brundtland report gave a definition of sustainable development as meeting "the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs" [7]. This defines needs from a human standpoint; as Lee (2000, p32) [8] has argued "sustainable development is an unashamedly anthropocentric concept"

The concept of sustainable development represents a shift in understanding of humanity's place on the planet, but it is open to interpretation of being anything from almost meaningless to of extreme importance to humanity. As well as, using the term of sustainability within the tourism context, it is clearly an area of contention. Whilst recognising the deep debates and ambiguities about the meaning of sustainable development, this paper uses the phrase "sustainable development" to describe attempts to combine concerns with the environment and socio-economic issues. To aid understanding of the sustainable development in the context of tourism, the author would like to clarify the sub-ideas of environment and socio-economic issues from the aspect of tourism as the basis concept. Critical analyze the environmental concerns within tourism aspects, the eco-tourism possibly come out first from your consideration.

Sustainability is found at the heart of rural policy with the ideal of achieving sustainable rural development a key dimension of EU, national, regional and local policy in recent years [10].

III. METHODOLOGY

A study of community-based destination sustainable development: Case of Cicada Walking Street, Hua Hin, Thailand is aim to study the role and activities of the participants and the impact of activities created in the local area. This study was to undertake and applied both qualitative and quantitative approaches, presented in descriptive style; the data was collected via survey, observation and in-depth interviews with samples.

A. The Study Area of Hua Hin, Thailand

Hua Hin, as shown in Fig. 1, the area map of Hua Hin, Prachaup Khiri Khan Province, Thailand is considered an area that has been highly development in the various fields such as tourism and economic of the area's rapid growth.

Fig. 1 Hua Hin community and the local nearby areas

Many developments have been properly but something was oblivious such as history, identity, cultures, arts, environmental and social of traditional Hua Hin. However, the area would not only be developed as well as movement of the physiological and economically that can compete with other country but also considered the affects of community

development in the future especially for the physical characteristic.

In the area of the case study, (Hua Hin community as shown in Fig. 1), covers both cultural and natural of the coastal line of Prachaup Khiri Khan Province, Thailand. At present this location near by the centre of growth that the comprehensive plan set for commercial and density residential area. As a result of several people came to area that determine the effects of urbanization.

B. Samples of the Research

This study sites were selected to in-depth interviews and questionnaire of three hundred samples, households, working people, sale persons and visitors random within the area of study.

IV. FINDINGS & RESULT

The Cicada walking street was an activity that hasn't the longest walking street in Thailand but currently the most interesting one, filled with contemporary creative tourism activity. There are four patterns of activities arranged in different venues. Location and avenues that are unique than other, made this pedestrian and the walking street is alive. It is not just a form of activity that was set up to be outstanding, but the different sorts of pedestrians are truly impetus the creative tourist activities of ,Cicada Market and walking street, here to be sustainable. The finding of roles and activities of people, who participated in the Cicada walking-street, found that the pedestrians walking can be identified as five groups of people; the property and activities management team, the merchants, the tourists, the leisure group and the local villagers who living in the local area.

Fig. 2 Roles and activities of people, who participated in the Cicada market and walking-street

Therefore, in this part, the roles and activities of people who join the walking street, will be explored and described in details as follows.

A. The Property and Activities Management Team

As the area of Cicada market and walking is the community shopping area that created by the intelligent of the private company called Sasi ampai Leisure Business Co., Ltd. works coordinate with the local community and local government. The stakeholder of Cicada are, therefore, very various. The property and activity management team are mainly come from the company part while the garbage, and the transportations were managed by the local community and government.

B. The Merchant Group Contains Many Types of Sales Together

Arranging and managing the walking street is positively affects to both the old merchants and the new entry operators. An emerging merchant has paid attentions to participate as the seller of varieties product. Considering in term of product, many retail sales have taken a variety of product types including, handicraft products, arts, crafts, accessories, healthy products and OTOP products. On the other hand the service provided on the walking street are mostly focus foods and beverages services, then health service such as Thai traditional massage services for example.

Entrepreneurs at the walking-street have a wide range of age groups. Almost half (48 percentages) of the sellers are external entrepreneurs, some of them move to live nearby and some of them take the public transport to come and sell their products on the weekend. Another half (45 percentages) of the merchants are originate from this province who see the opportunities to earn money from the tourists so they start their business from their strengths such as local food sales for example. And the rest of people (about 7 percentages) have their own permanent career and doing this night shift as their part-time job or side-line job, some do for happiness but mostly economically.

The products that sold in the walking-street are well managed, by the area their shop located, the type of goods and the uniqueness of the products. As mentioned at the first stage that the Cicada Market and walking street were divided into different zones with individual theme identified, the shop in each area therefore managed to sell the products that suit with the theme. The type of the product and the uniqueness of the goods mean that they must offer something that different from other sellers. For example, in the area of food there are a shop sells a spicy seafood noodle. The new entry cannot sell exactly the same thing.

C. The Group of Tourist

The tourists both internal tourist and the international tourist come to travel to Hua Hin a lot as it is one of the popular destinations not so far from the capital city, Bangkok. Group of tourists who visit the Cicada market and walking street can be divided into 3 tourist groups; the local tourists, the tourist from other provinces and group of international tourists. The first group, local tourist are the people who living in the same province usually come for relaxing and spending their time with family and friends approximately one to two times a month. The second group, tourist from other provinces, the

largest group of customers, visits this place as a group of family usually comes for relaxing and spending their time with family and friends approximately one to two times a month. Majority of the people in this group are originating from Bangkok or living and working in the capital city. The last group, foreigner tourists, most of the foreigners who travel to Hua Hin and visit the Cicada Market and walking-street known the place from the introduction staged on the guild book such the lonely planet for example. The second larger amount of international tourist got the local area information from the hotel information desk. The smallest numbers of international tourist were guided by the tour company. Majority of the international tourist are in the age between twenty to thirty years old, thirty-one to forty-one years old and ten to nineteen years old respectively. Mostly come with the propose of leisure time, a break from their school and works or travel as the family also normal visible in the destinations.

D. The Leisure Group

Leisure activities, sometimes called as recreations on the walking Street are both the activities from various agencies artists, which will be held on the stage activities will be substituted for each week and an independent artists including street artists comprised of local musicians, universal music Interestingly, there are four main types of creative activities presented here; art based, cultural based and live events. Art based activities refer to the activities that integrate the knowledge and the performances based on various types of arts such performance arts, fine arts, literature arts and etc. The arts based activities are mostly individual presented. Cultural based activities combines the local lifestyles, traditional, arts and cultures into the activities mainly the activities are group presented. Last, the live events claim to all live performance which no need to play on stage, emphasis on the action that is real and actually happen and make the area alive. Street magic shows, clay man on the street, group of b-boy and hip-hop dances are all included.

The characteristics of a group of independent artists available on the street can be separated group of students, workers, and the elderly. A group of students and the senior artist are mostly present the local performances to entertain the local audients while, the university student and the middle age working classes are more variety, some perform the international music, some of good painters and some stage performances.

Most of the work will be the universal music artists, painters and actors. These artists are all local people. And those who come to studies or works in the area.

E. The Local Villagers who Living in the Local Area

On the same street and area, there are many types of places and residents; tourist destinations, restaurants, historical sites, guesthouse, shops, temples and houses.

The main street villagers can be separate into three categories. First the residential houses mostly are not located on the main road, especially the area directly opposite to the walking-street. Only few on the residents who long-time lives

there before the walking-street occur, they do not want to more and find another way of living there with a little profit earn by lent the car parks. Second, the stores or the retail shop on the main street, as the result of the creative walking street built and made this place became the popular tourist destination, the land and location prices was double raise up high. The types of stores that available on the main street are mostly own by the chain company or a big investors such as a huge seafood restaurants, franchise grocery stores, local tour company and the all-in-one souvenirs shop for example. Last group is the temple and historical sites, Cicada market and walking street locate just next to the mountain called 'KhaoTakeab' or known as the chopstick mountain, where the famous temple 'WatKhaoTakeab' located at the top of the mountain.

It also illustrates that there are four essential elements to make the market and walking street work well to attract more visitors as well as keep the destination become sustainable tourist destination development. The four elements mentioned are people, place, uniqueness and free trading policy.

First, begin with people, as the hardest thing to manage. As long as the human resource are good and work effectively, the company or firm will be successful easily. A good example of Cicada market and walking street, most people responsible their own duties and respect to each other therefore it is successful in many ways. Second, the element of place, this includes convenient location, clean and energizing atmosphere and area design decoration that give such a good feelings, worm, romance, free, safe while quit private and etc. Then, uniqueness that combines many differences such the differences of local traditions, arts and cultures in various ways such as local performances, local foods, local art and crafts and local celebrations to be one unique. Last, free trading policy is applied to flow the economy of the area. It is simple key of selling things cheaper strategy.

The study of impacts of cicada market to the local areas shown many good impacts on local communities are those in terms of economy, environmental friendly and local arts and cultures promoting. On the other hand, the traffic congestion, waste and the increasing of energy consumption are increased as the bad effects from destination development.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Participants are various. The roles of the participants found in the Cicada Market are group of the property and area management, entrepreneurs, leisure (entertaining persons), local people, and tourists.

The good impacts on local communities are those in terms of economy, environmental friendly and local arts and cultures promoting. On the other hand, the traffic congestion, waste and the increasing of energy consumption are increased as the effects from development.

From the findings illustrated the strength of this creative community based tourism activity while showing the disadvantages of its, therefore, in order to use this model as the role model for other tourism destination it might be better to get ready and prevent the disadvantage that might be

happen follow the development. The garbage management, proper car park arranging and a clear signs and signal to help the traffic flow better might be alternatives in this case.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Thailand Tourism Review. Bangkokpost.com. Retrieved on 2010-09-16.
- [2] Kristene Quan (1 June 2013). "And the World's No. 1 Tourist Destination Is ...". *Time*. Time Inc. Retrieved 3 June 2013.
- [3] Ben Abramson (31 December 2013). "Most popular photo locations on Instagram in 2013". *USA Today*. Retrieved 9 January 2014.
- [4] Caroline Ashley and Elizabeth Garland. (1994) Promoting Community-Based Tourism Development: Why, What and How? Research Discussion Paper. October 1994.
- [5] Hopwood, B., Mellor, M. and O'Brien, G. Sustainable Development: mapping different approaches. *Sustainable Development*, 13. pp. 38-52. (2005).
- [6] IUCN, UNEP & WWF. World Conservation Strategy: Living Resource Conservation for Sustainable Development. IUCN: Gland, Switzerland (1980).
- [7] WCED (World Commission on Environment and Development). Our Common Future. Oxford University Press: Oxford. (1987).
- [8] Lee K. Global Sustainable Development: Its Intellectual and Historical Roots. In *Global Sustainable Development in the 21st Century*. Lee K, Holland A, McNeill D (eds). Edinburgh University Press: Edinburgh. (2000).
- [9] SasiAmpai Leisure Business. About us "Cicada Market". Retrieved from <http://www.cicadamarket.com/en>. Retrieved at 07/12/2012. (2013).
- [10] McDonagh, J., T. Varley and S. Shortallds. A living countryside? The politics of sustainable development in rural Ireland (Aldershot: Ashgate) (2009).
- [11] Liu, Z. (2003) Sustainable tourism development: a critique. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, Vol.11 (No.6). pp. 459-475. ISSN 0966-9582.
- [12] PhaisalLekuthai., Discussion Paper No. 168 Lanna Culture and Social Development: A Case Study of Chiangmai Province in Northern Thailand.(2008).

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